

Leveraging Satellite Constellations to Boost 5G Reliability for Connected Livestock Transport

Matthieu Petrou
Viveris Technologies
Toulouse, France
matthieu.petrou@viveris.fr

Mathias Ettinger
Viveris Technologies
Toulouse, France
mathias.ettinger@viveris.fr

Santiago Garcia-Guillen
CNES
Toulouse, France
santiago.garciaguillen@cnes.fr

Alejandro Ramírez-Arroyo
Department of Electronic Systems
Aalborg University (AAU)
Aalborg, Denmark
araar@es.aau.dk

David Pradas
Viveris Technologies
Toulouse, France
david.pradas@viveris.fr

Abstract—Ensuring reliable connectivity in rural areas remains a challenge, especially for mobile applications requiring real-time data exchange. In this study, we investigate the feasibility of multi-connectivity solutions combining terrestrial and satellite networks to improve communication reliability for livestock transport trucks in Europe, addressing both short-term and mid-term requirements. We conducted real-world mobility experiments using vehicles equipped with narrowband satellite access for tracking needs, alongside broadband cellular (4G/5G) and satellite connectivity, simultaneously transmitting duplicated traffic to ensure seamless access for future services. Our results show that satellite-assisted duplication significantly reduces packet loss in scenarios where cellular networks are unreliable. Additionally, we analyze end-to-end latency, packet arrival times, and derive Gilbert-Elliott model parameters from real-world measurements. We conclude that while the duplication approach is highly viable, it comes with trade-offs, including increased bandwidth consumption and the need for improved congestion control mechanisms.

Index Terms—5G, satellite, packet duplication, livestock transport, mobility

I. INTRODUCTION

While 5G provides sufficient connectivity for IoT and Industry 4.0 applications, its deployment remains primarily focused on densely populated areas, leaving rural regions with limited connectivity solutions. One promising alternative is the use of satellite networks to complement mobile networks and provide coverage where terrestrial infrastructure falls short. This approach is being investigated by the COMECT project [1], which aims at bridging the digital divide, by providing quality, reliable, and secure access for all in rural and remote areas. The expansion of broadband connectivity in rural and remote areas will be accomplished by integrating Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) with Terrestrial Networks (TN), such as XG networks [2], along with cost-effective Internet of Things (IoT) solutions.

This paper focuses on the specific use case of connected trucks transporting livestock across European roads, where reliable connectivity is essential for regulatory compliance and

real-time monitoring. Livestock transportation must comply with strict health and safety regulations, including continuous GPS tracking of transport vehicles and real-time monitoring of environmental conditions within livestock compartments. Furthermore, a more connected approach to livestock transport could enhance safety and optimize logistics, ensuring better animal welfare. However, these advancements are hindered by the limitations of cellular network coverage, particularly in rural areas.

To address this challenge, we evaluate the feasibility of multi-connectivity solutions that leverage both satellite communications (SATCOM) and terrestrial mobile networks. To assess its effectiveness, we conduct real-world mobility experiments using a van equipped with both narrowband (Iridium Short Data Burst - SBD) and broadband (OneWeb and Starlink) satellite connections, alongside a terrestrial mobile network link. By transmitting UDP traffic, we analyze the performance of satellite-assisted communication in reducing packet loss on mobile networks.

In addition to packet loss analysis, we investigate end-to-end latency and packet arrival times under different mobility scenarios. Finally, we provide Gilbert-Elliott model parameters based on real-world loss measurements, offering valuable reference data for the research community.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the motivation and technical background of this paper. Section III describes the methodology used to collect the data on the real life scenarios. Section IV compares the performance of mobile and satellite links, and evaluates the benefits of packet duplication. Finally, Section V concludes this study.

II. MOTIVATION AND TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

This section examines the challenges of connectivity in livestock transportation and the growing demand for reliable communication in rural areas. It also offers a technical overview of narrowband and broadband satellite solutions and

their potential to address these challenges. Lastly, it explores multi-connectivity strategies and their benefits.

A. Challenges of livestock transportation

Livestock transport plays a crucial role in the supply chain of animal breeding and production. To ensure animal welfare during transportation, as well as during loading and unloading operations, it is essential to comply with regulations. Some of these regulations mandate both digital data transmission between livestock transport units and the operational center throughout the journey. For instance, in pig transport between the consignor and consignee farms, every movement must be recorded in the Pig Movement Database [3]. As a result, further digitalization of livestock transport could offer significant benefits, enhancing cost efficiency while ensuring compliance, animal welfare, and livestock quality.

Regulations on animal protection during transport mandate continuous reporting of the truck's location at fixed intervals of 10 to 12 minutes. Currently, these location reports are transmitted over 2G networks (in the process of migrating to 4G), but poor cellular connectivity often leads to transmission failures between the truck and the coordination center. In addition to location tracking, continuous monitoring of animal health and other critical parameters is required during transport. This includes onboard sensor data such as CO₂ levels, temperature inside the livestock compartments, load weight, and the status of the loading ramp. However, this information is currently recorded manually and only uploaded to regulatory databases after the journey is completed, rather than being transmitted in real time. Livestock transport companies have expressed a need for monitoring information to be transmitted alongside the truck's position every 1 to 5 minutes [4].

Stakeholders, including transport companies, are envisioning a more intelligent and connected approach to livestock transport, where large volumes of data are continuously shared with transport centers and regulatory bodies, improving safety and optimizing the trading process. Livestock transporters must carefully plan each journey to avoid restricted areas, such as zones at risk of infection (e.g., swine fever), and ensure travel times remain under 24 hours. However, unexpected events such as traffic congestion, road closures, or fluctuating temperatures can make this challenging. To address these issues, there is a demand for an onboard display that provides real-time route optimization for navigation. Such a system requires seamless connectivity with sufficient capacity to load maps, access real-time traffic conditions, consult live traffic cameras, retrieve information on restricted areas, and check weather forecasts for dynamic route adjustments.

Another key application is the continuous online reporting of sensor data, enabling remote monitoring of trailer conditions. This allows trading companies to proactively detect potential issues and provide real-time support to truck drivers, ensuring safer and more efficient livestock transport. By enabling continuous data exchange between transport units and operational centers, a smarter livestock trading system could be achieved. The exchange of relevant data in almost real-

Fig. 1: Illustration of cellular and satellite multi-connectivity for livestock transport between two farms.

time will help minimizing the trip time and thus improving animal wellness and driver's quality of life, and reduce energy consumption.

Seamless connectivity between transport units and the operational center is a critical requirement, both in the short- and long-term, to meet these objectives effectively.

Despite claims from cellular operators, vehicles relying on cellular networks (2G/3G/4G/5G) often experience unstable connectivity, particularly in rural areas and on secondary roads, sometimes even losing service [4]. Additionally, 5G coverage remains limited in many remote areas where farms are typically located. Rural regions are often underserved by operators, leading to insufficient service quality for various applications. Consequently, cellular access alone cannot guarantee seamless and reliable connectivity across all roads and farm locations.

Multi-connectivity, or hybrid strategies that combine multiple networks or technologies, emerged years ago as a solution to improve reliability. Today, it remains a crucial approach in modern networks, addressing the growing demand for seamless, reliable, and high-speed connectivity. Multi-connectivity in the last-mile network—leveraging both TN and NTN at the user terminal and in the access and backhauling network presents a promising solution for achieving seamless and reliable connectivity. As illustrated in Fig. 1, here we focus in the last-mile network where satellite connectivity can serve as a backup when cellular coverage is insufficient or unavailable along the livestock transport route.

B. Multi-connectivity strategies for broadband services

The need for seamless connectivity cannot override other needs/requirements. The objective is to propose multi-connectivity solutions allowing to transmit/receive data frequently by means of a combination of wireless technologies but not at all costs; a trade-off must be found between the following challenges:

- Reduce energy consumption: From an ecological perspective, using two wireless technologies increases carbon footprint if they are not used correctly. One link should be used primarily, with both enabled only when necessary.

- Optimize bandwidth use: An overuse of bandwidth is not fair in terms of carbon footprint and cost.
- Service reliability: This is a challenging condition for many use cases and especially for livestock transport, where missing the localization information during a 10 to 12 minute time window might have a huge impact.
- Maximize Quality of Experience (QoE): Once previous requirements are met, the user QoE must be considered, in particular for interactive applications, where available Uplink/Downlink throughput and eventually the Round-Trip-Time (RTT) need to be optimized.

To find the best trade-off under mobility conditions, three traffic engineering strategies are discussed: packet duplications, dynamic routing and Multi Path TCP (MPTCP).

Packet duplication across two links is a strategy used to achieve the lowest possible latency and maximum reliability, but at the cost of higher bandwidth consumption. This strategy is indeed able to minimize packet losses if configured correctly but might increase energy/bandwidth consumption if both links are used simultaneously for long time.

Minimizing bandwidth usage is crucial for ecological reasons, and a dynamic routing strategy between two links can help achieve this. In this case, a smart scheduler/router can switch the traffic flows from one link to the other depending on different policies or the status of the networks. This strategy aims to minimize energy consumption and bandwidth usage but may lead to packet drops if not properly managed under fluctuating link conditions. This will impact bandwidth use efficiency and reduce the QoE if the system is not tuned correctly.

The last envisaged strategy, MPTCP [5], is an effort towards enabling the simultaneous use of several IP addresses/interfaces/networks by a modification of TCP that is transparent for the applications, while in fact spreading data across several subflows. Benefits of this include a more efficient resource utilization (depending on the chosen policy), higher throughput and smoother reaction to failures, but it is only available for TCP-based services. MPTCP could be a promising alternative, but in its current implementation, only the default mode (congestion window based) is available using both links simultaneously. Therefore, the more suitable for our case backup mode is not available. Its excessive goodput consumption, due to aggregating bandwidth, prevents it from being a viable candidate.

In previous emulation experiments performed with our metrology test bench OpenBACH [6], we evaluated two approaches—dynamic routing and duplication—under extreme loss conditions (50-90%) on the emulated cellular link using TCP/CUBIC flows.

- The main challenge with dynamic routing is its responsiveness; if the system fails to react in time, TCP/CUBIC suffers a significant performance drop and takes time to recover.
- Duplication, on the other hand, remains unaffected by losses, as lost packets are recovered through redundant

transmission. To mitigate excessive bandwidth consumption, Maurya et al. [7] are able to accurately predict cellular network unavailability to efficiently enable a smart packet duplication.

Based on the results of our emulation tests [8], the broadband tests in Section IV will implement the duplication strategy, as it offers the highest reliability. When applied, smart duplication presents a well-balanced cost-efficiency.

C. Narrowband and Broadband Satellite Solutions: Balancing Present Needs and Future Innovations

The latest IoT Analytics “State of IoT-Spring 2023” report [9] shows that global IoT connections grew by 18% in 2022 to 14.3 billion active IoT endpoints. Short-range wireless technologies (Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and Zigbee) and longer-range connectivity technologies, such as Long Range (LoRa), Narrowband IoT and Long-Term Evolution for Machines (LTE-M) are simplifying the development of IoT sensor data collection at a fair cost. However, connectivity using terrestrial-based Low-Power Wide-Area Networks (LPWAN) is only possible where there is access to a terrestrial network, which is often not the case, such as trucks fleet tracking. For these applications satellite communication is the only feasible option.

Historically, only very high volume or extremely mission-critical applications could justify the high cost of satellite access. This growing popularity of small satellites is opening multiple opportunities to implement satellite technologies for remote sensing. Using broadband satellite access only for sensor data collection has not yet been justified, given the high price of broadband satellite capacity and the price of the mobile antenna for one single truck. However, satellite operators propose dedicated transport service with cheaper equipment/antennas: either booking low priority data for this kind of traffic, like Iridium SBD service and Inmarsat IsatData Pro (IDP) or building dedicated constellations for sensor data collection (like Lacuna Space). These solutions provide low-bandwidth, global coverage, making it a valuable solution for basic tracking and monitoring needs. In livestock transport, they could enable periodic position updates, temperature and humidity monitoring inside trailers, and emergency alerts, ensuring compliance with regulations and animal welfare requirements. Its ability to function even in remote areas where cellular networks are unavailable makes it a critical short-term solution and a long-term option for dedicated services that require only small data transmissions.

In recent years, however, the cost of access to space has been decreasing, with organizations such as Starlink or OneWeb dramatically driving down launch costs, stimulating growth in the launch numbers of small satellites, including CubeSats. While narrowband is sufficient for basic monitoring, broadband satellite access will be essential for future, data-intensive applications. These solutions would allow livestock transport companies to stream live camera feeds from inside trailers for remote supervision, enable real-time route optimization based on live traffic and weather data, support AI-driven predictive maintenance for transport vehicles and

(a) OSCAR van

(b) Top of the van

Fig. 2: OSCAR van and the top of the van showing Starlink antenna (left side), MAGW with 5G modem (center) and OneWeb antenna (right side).

enhance communication between drivers, logistics centers, and regulatory authorities.

In the following sections, we evaluate these satellite technologies to complement the cellular 4G/5G network, addressing the needs of livestock transport, balancing narrowband solutions for immediate, low-data applications and broadband solutions for advanced, future-oriented services.

III. TESTBED

A. Narrowband

Iridium Short Burst Data (SBD) is a satellite-based communication service designed for short, efficient data transmissions. It is commonly used in remote applications such as asset tracking, environmental monitoring, maritime communications, and military operations.

In our test, we connect the Iridium SBD device to a PC, which serves as our narrowband satellite access. The system operates as follows:

- 1) the SBD device transmits the data (GPS/sensor) from the PC as a short message (typically up to 340 bytes uplink);
- 2) the message is sent to the nearest Iridium satellite;

- 3) the satellite then relays the message to an Iridium ground station;
- 4) the ground station processes the data and forwards it to our IP-based server or sends it via email.

We tested the device under mobility conditions by mounting it on the top of a car traveling through rural areas, as well as on the roof of a building for stationary evaluation.

B. Broadband

We use the OSCAR van, owned by CNES and part of CESARS Expertise Center [10], to carry out the test performance campaigns. OSCAR has been designed to evaluate the performance of real satellite antennas and SATCOM services from the market under mobility conditions and to demonstrate SATCOM on the Move. The van includes onboard equipment such as GPS, Inertial reference systems, satellite modems and antennas, NUC servers and monitoring/supervision tools. In our case, the vehicle integrates two satellite antennas, from OneWeb and Starlink shown in the right side and the left side of the van roof shown in Fig. 2, respectively, allowing access to LEO satellite constellations. Between both antennas, we have integrated a Multi-Access GateWay (MAGW) that enables seamless and technology-agnostic wireless control communication.

The main element of the MAGW is an ARM-based Gateworks GW6405 industrial computer. This is a small computer, which supports up to four mini-PCIe extension cards, 5 ethernet ports that allow connection of different devices, for example, cellular modems, WiFi cards, and Ethernet-based communication devices. In our case, we use one cellular modem employing a SIM card from a French operator. The Ethernet port is used to connect to the satellite modem.

The MAGW incorporates the mpconn tunneling program [11]. It performs multi-connectivity by duplicating Layer 3 packets and transmitting them over IP using Layer 4 packets UDP. It can do so through the same or different systems, making a versatile tool for evaluating multi-connectivity performance in different scenarios, even when the active links encompass different technologies. In our case, the two links used for duplication are cellular 5G and satellite.

During tests, both links are used simultaneously, and when mpconn is enabled, all packets are duplicated. This setup allows us to compare packet arrival times and identify losses on either or both links. For our tests, we use iperf3 [12] to transmit UDP packets at a rate of 15 Mbps (downlink) according to the requirements defined in COMECT for livestock transport [13]. This paper focuses on UDP traffic to accurately estimate the available bandwidth and packet. TCP traffic will be addressed in future work.

For the performance tests, we have two mobility scenarios. The first scenario takes place in an area with extremely poor operator coverage (between Caujac and Gaillac-Toulza, in France) at speeds around 50km/h, resulting in high packet loss on the cellular link, which we refer to as *High-Loss Mobility* in the rest of this paper. The second scenario involves the van traveling between Toulouse and the low-coverage area, which

we refer to as *Round-Trip Mobility* in the rest of this paper. While the van can drive at higher speeds (70-110 km/h), this area has significantly better coverage, leading to much lower expected packet loss.

IV. MOBILITY TEST PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

This section presents the results of narrowband satellite tests and the broadband satellite mobility tests, focusing on latency, packet loss, and an analysis of the benefits and drawbacks of packet duplication. We discuss the impact of duplication on network performance, both the improvements in reliability and the challenges related to system deployment and resource usage.

A. Narrowband Latency

As detailed below, we evaluated the performance of SBD latency and reliability under two different conditions:

- On the top of a moving car driving through rural areas with poor cellular coverage (between Toulouse and Samatan) at speeds of 60–90 km/h, with various obstacles along the route, including hills, trees, and houses;
- On the roof of the Viveris building, where sky visibility was generally good, except for some surrounding trees.

During the test, a message was sent every minute. The devices assessed signal strength with the available satellite and transmit only when the signal was sufficiently strong. Once an acknowledgment was received from the gateway (GW), the message was marked as successfully delivered. From a reliability standpoint, all messages were correctly received by our remote server. Regarding latency, the cumulative distribution function of the total transmission time is shown in Fig. 3. This includes the time to get enough signal strength and the acknowledgment from the remote side. The difference between the mobile and static scenarios is minimal, with a median latency of 10 seconds for the roof setup and 11 seconds for the mobile setup. These values align with those reported in [14] and are attributed to the low priority of these messages within the Iridium infrastructure. This suggests that satellite availability and visibility are the primary factors affecting latency. However, in 10–15% of the tests, mobility conditions did have an impact, increasing latency by approximately 20–30 s seconds.

These results demonstrate that Iridium SBD is a reliable solution that can be deployed to meet livestock transport requirements. It successfully transmits tracking and sensor data every two minutes in 98% of cases, with the worst-case transmission time reaching approximately 150 seconds for both conditions.

B. Latency

We use ping to monitor the RTT of both Starlink and OneWeb satellite links over time. Fig. 4 shows the CDF of the RTT for both links. The figure highlights the latency difference between the two satellite operators. While Starlink RTT varies between 15 ms and 100 ms, OneWeb RTT ranges from 80 ms to more than one second. This difference is expected because

Fig. 3: CDF of Iridium SBD Total sending time (s)

Fig. 4: CDF of RTT of Starlink and OneWeb satellite link.

they are based on different LEO satellite constellations at different orbits; around 1,200 km for OneWeb and 340-614 km for Starlink.

However, the altitude difference alone does not fully account for the observed latency gap, as the propagation delay due to the speed of light would only double the latency value. Other contributing factors likely include the distribution and number of ground stations—Starlink have more ground stations in Europe than OneWeb. Additionally, network congestion and architecture likely play a role in the higher and more variable RTT observed with OneWeb.

Fig. 5 illustrates the arrival time differences between the satellite and cellular links across all scenarios. Negative values indicate that the packet from the satellite link arrived before the packet from the cellular link. Note that this figure does not account for lost packets on either link, as their arrival times cannot be compared in this case. In the Round-Trip Mobility scenario, only around 10% of packets arrive from the OneWeb link before packets from the cellular link, while approximately a third of packets arrive from the Starlink link before the cellular one. In the High-Loss Mobility scenario, around 40% of the packets arrive on the OneWeb link before the mobile one, and the majority (55%) arrive on the Starlink link before the mobile one.

Starlink can deliver a packet up to 10 s ahead of the cellular

Fig. 5: CDF of Relative Packet Arrival Times: Satellite - Mobile. Negative values indicate the satellite delivers packets first; positive values indicate the cellular link delivers packets first.

link, but it can also be delayed by a maximum of 100 ms. By contrast, the OneWeb link can be faster than the cellular link by only a few seconds at most and can be delayed by several seconds.

This supports the findings in Fig. 4, confirming that Starlink is faster than OneWeb. The difference is not negligible, especially when comparing practical performance in packet duplications.

C. Packet Loss

In this section, we measure and analyze the end-to-end packet loss observed in the mobility scenarios. We compare the loss ratio across the cellular link, the satellite link, and their combined mobile-satellite duplication. Finally, we estimate and provide the parameters of a simplified Gilbert-Elliott model, which can be used by the research community to emulate these links realistically.

1) *Round-Trip Mobility Scenario*: Fig. 6a and Fig. 6b present the CDF of the loss ratio in the Round-Trip Mobility scenario using mobile-satellite duplication with Starlink and OneWeb, respectively. These figures highlight a significant difference in the satellite link loss ratio between the two tests. In the Starlink test, the mobile network experiences packet loss in 40% of the monitored seconds, whereas in the OneWeb test, losses occur in less than 10% of the time. As a result, a direct comparison between the mobile and duplication results is not feasible.

Fig.6a illustrates that duplication substantially mitigates packet loss. While the cellular and satellite links individually experience loss in 40% and 20% of the monitored seconds, respectively, duplication reduces the losses to less than 5%, with a significantly lower overall loss rate. Similarly, Fig.6b shows that duplication nearly eliminates packet loss (0.04%), whereas the satellite and cellular links individually experience losses in approximately 5% of the monitored seconds.

Additionally, the higher loss rate observed on the Starlink link compared to OneWeb suggests a degradation in perfor-

mance at higher mobility speeds. However, further experiments would be required to confirm.

2) *High-Loss Mobility Scenario*: Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b present the CDF of the loss ratio in the High-Loss Mobility scenario using mobile-satellite duplication with Starlink and OneWeb, respectively. As in the previous section, the loss patterns on the cellular link differ between the two tests. In the Starlink test, the mobile network experiences packet loss in more than 70% of the monitored seconds, whereas in the OneWeb test, losses occur in over 80% of the time. Although the Starlink link has packet loss in approximately 25% of the monitored seconds, its overall loss ratio remains lower than that of the OneWeb link. The latter exhibits losses in only 20% of the monitored seconds but with a higher loss ratio during those periods. In both cases, the duplication loss rate closely follows the satellite link loss rate, as the cellular link proves unreliable in this scenario.

3) *Estimation of Gilbert-Elliott Model Parameters*: From the packet loss traces, we estimate the transition probabilities of a simplified Gilbert-Elliott model [15], [16]. Table I summarizes the calculated parameters. The parameters follow the notation $P_{(s_{new}|s_{old})}$, as proposed in RFC6534 [17], where s_{new} represents the new state and s_{old} the previous state. The states are either *Good* (g) or *Bad* (b). In the *Good* state, all packets are received, whereas in the *Bad* state, all packets are lost. The table also reports the average loss rate for each scenario.

The mean loss values demonstrate that duplication effectively mitigates packet loss. On the Round-Trip Mobility scenarios, starting from a loss ratio of 5.77% and 0.83% on the cellular link, and 3.25% and 1.66% on the Starlink and OneWeb links, respectively, duplication reduces the loss to just 0.15% and 0.04%. On the High-Loss Mobility scenarios, the duplication mainly helps the cellular links: from a loss ratio of 64.50% and 79.52%, duplication reduces the loss to 3.12% and 7.20%, which is very close to the loss rate of the satellite link (3.95% and 8.63% for Starlink and OneWeb).

From these results, we could argue that duplication is useful for complementing the cellular link but less beneficial for the satellite link, as it does not significantly improve satellite performance. However, it is important to note that the High-Loss Mobility scenario is specifically chosen for its high loss on the cellular link. In a scenario where the satellite link experiences high loss instead, the results would likely be reversed. Overall, it is important to emphasize that the Gilbert-Elliott model allow us to simulate these conditions in our lab to assess the performance of various mechanisms and strategies.

D. Guidelines

This section summarizes the findings of our mobility tests, highlighting differences between Starlink and OneWeb. Additionally, it evaluates the impact of packet duplication.

Starlink exhibits significantly lower latency, with packets arriving earlier than on the cellular link in 30–55% of cases. In contrast, OneWeb has a higher overall latency and provides a lower delay than the cellular link in only 10% of the cases in

(a) Starlink

(b) OneWeb

Fig. 6: CDF of packet loss ratio in the Round-Trip Mobility scenario for Starlink and OneWeb (starting from 0.5 as there are no losses below this threshold).

(a) Starlink

(b) OneWeb

Fig. 7: CDF of packet loss ratio in the High-Loss Mobility scenario for Starlink and OneWeb.

TABLE I: Overview of Gilbert-Elliott model parameters for each scenario.

Scenario	Satellite Provider	Cellular Link			Satellite Link			Duplication		
		$P_{(b g)}$	$P_{(g b)}$	loss (%)	$P_{(b g)}$	$P_{(g b)}$	loss (%)	$P_{(b g)}$	$P_{(g b)}$	loss (%)
Round-Trip Mobility	Starlink	0.003349	0.054681	5.77%	0.000617	0.018336	3.25%	0.000083	0.053410	0.15%
	OneWeb	0.000652	0.077832	0.83%	0.000149	0.008815	1.66%	0.000004	0.010204	0.04%
High-Loss Mobility	Starlink	0.001462	0.000805	64.50%	0.000453	0.011024	3.95%	0.000365	0.011331	3.12%
	OneWeb	0.010147	0.002613	79.52%	0.000404	0.004274	8.63%	0.000411	0.005302	7.20%

the Round-Trip Mobility scenario and 40% in the High-Loss Mobility scenario.

In terms of packet loss, Starlink appears to be less resilient at higher mobility speeds. Further experiments are required to determine whether this behavior is due to specific test conditions or an inherent characteristic of the system. Nonetheless, the difference between Starlink and OneWeb remains relatively small, with only a 1.5% difference in packet loss. In the High-Loss Mobility scenario, OneWeb experienced approximately 5% more packet loss than Starlink. Additional testing would also be necessary to assess whether this trend is consistent

across different conditions.

Table II summarizes the potential benefits of packet duplication to improve connectivity in rural mobility scenarios. Although duplication offers improvements in overall performance, particularly in mitigating losses and reducing latency, it is important to assess whether these benefits justify the additional operational costs. Maintaining two simultaneous links (satellite and cellular) for packet duplication may incur costs that outweigh the performance benefits, particularly when the cellular link is not heavily congested or the satellite link alone is sufficient. However, enabling duplication only when

TABLE II: Potential gains and compromises from duplication over flow performance and deployment.

	Gain	Compromise
Performance	Reduces overall losses Lowers end-to-end latency Mitigates impact of handovers	TCP congestion control may overload one link when throughput is unbalanced
Deployment	Increases resilience in high-loss environments	Higher energy consumption Higher bandwidth consumption (if not smart) Increased network costs

necessary (smart duplication), as demonstrated by Maurya et al. [7], helps minimize the bandwidth consumption impact of using both links. For TCP/QUIC-based services, traditional congestion control algorithms do not account for packet duplication, which can lead to inefficient utilization of network resources by overloading the links. This can interfere with other traffic, unnecessarily degrading the overall performance. Therefore, developing congestion control algorithms optimized for packet duplication may be essential to prevent the pitfalls of overburdening the network.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we evaluate the benefits of multi-connectivity between SATCOM and terrestrial mobile networks to enhance the connection reliability of livestock transport trucks. We conduct real-world mobility experiments using vehicles equipped with both narrowband and broadband satellite access equipment alongside cellular modems, to analyze the effectiveness of satellite-assisted communication in enhancing connection reliability through a packet duplication strategy.

Our results show that narrowband satellite communication is well-suited for specialized, low-power applications such as basic tracking, emergency alerts, and status reporting in areas with intermittent connectivity. In contrast, broadband satellite tests demonstrate that new LEO satellite constellations can significantly enhance reliability when cellular networks are unavailable, while also enabling higher data rates to support bandwidth-intensive applications expected to expand in the coming years.

Despite these benefits, packet duplication introduces new challenges, such as increased power consumption and potential congestion on one link when the other offers higher throughput.

As future work, we aim to further assess the viability of satellite links in mobility scenarios to determine whether a standalone satellite connection could meet livestock transportation requirements, even in conditions where satellite connectivity has traditionally been less reliable.

Additionally, we plan to explore mechanisms to prevent link overflow when duplication is used across connections with significant throughput differences.

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